

**QUEEN'S
UNIVERSITY
BELFAST**

3D printability of polymer blended/graphene composites for strain sensors applications

Liam O'Connor, Oana Istrate

School of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Queen's University Belfast

Contents

- Background
- Section of materials
- Experimental results
- FEA analysis
- Comparing to literature data
- Conclusions / future work

<https://www.med-technews.com>

Background

- ~3 million people require a prosthetic
- 62,000 people in the UK use prosthetics
- Rate of prosthetic abandonment is 44% for upper limbs

i-Limb

Be-bionic

Michelangelo

Background

Traditional manufacturing

Advanced manufacturing

Pressure sensors in prosthetics

- Pressure sensors provide a restored sensation.
- 3D printing allows greater freedom of design.
- Aim: Develop a model to accurately predict the mechanical properties.

3D Printing

- Stereolithography (SLA)
- Powder bed and inkjet head (PBIH) 3D printing
- Selective laser sintering (SLS)
- Fused deposition modelling (FDM)
 - Cost-efficient
 - Minimal material waste
 - Enables dual-material printing
 - Complex structures

Nanofillers

- Nanomaterials:

- Nanospheres
- Nanotubes
- Nanoplatelets
- Nanoparticles

- Carbon based nanomaterials:

- 0D (fullerenes)
- 1D (carbon nanotubes)
- 2D (graphene)
- 3D (graphite)

Polymer nanocomposites

- Composite in which at least one of the phase domains has at least one dimension of the order of nanometres
 - Matrix
 - Nanofiller
- Polymer nanocomposites can be manufactured through:
 - *In situ* polymerization
 - Solution blending
 - Melt mixing

Polymer blends

Polymer blends are divided into two categories

Polymer blend nanocomposites

- Graphene nanoplatelets have been successfully incorporated in PMMA/PEO and PC/ABS polymer blends
- FDM 3D printing was used to manufacture PLA/TPU polymer blended carbon nanocomposites for sensor applications

Selection of materials

3D printable			
Elastic	Strength		
TPU	PLA	ABS	PP

Internal voids between printlines

Infill pattern / density

Infill pattern	Equation
Triangle	$E = 1.15E_s \left(\frac{t}{l}\right)$
Square	$E = E_s \left(\frac{t}{l}\right)$
Hexagonal	$E = 2.3E_s \left(\frac{t}{l}\right)^3$
Direction	Equation
In-plane	$E_1 = (1 - p_1)E$
Out plane	$E_2 = (1 - \sqrt{p_1})E$

Predicting porosity

$$p_1 = \frac{H_0^2 \cos \theta - \left[\pi \left(\frac{H_0}{2} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{H_0}{2} \right)^2 (2\theta - \sin 2\theta) \right]}{H_0 w(t) + H_0^2 \cos \theta}$$

$$w(t) = w_0 + \frac{H_0 \theta}{\lambda} - \frac{H_0 \sin 2\theta}{\rho}$$

Experimental results of printing

- Stiffness has a linear relationship with infill density / rate controlled by infill pattern

Comparing experimental to modelled

Triangle

Square

Hexagonal

FEA

- The FEA study found that the stress-to-displacement ratio determines the rate of Young's modulus increase

Triangle

Square

Hexagonal

Correcting the model based on FEA

Triangle

Square

Hexagonal

Comparing to literature data

- The model under predicted for the polymers however over predicted for the polymer blend.

Conclusions

- The models in literature do not take into account the outer walls of the print
- Through FEA analysis the rate of change of stiffness with infill density is depended on the infill pattern
- Applying the knowledge from experimental and FEA analysis the model showed alignment with literature values

Future work

- Further model validation with different materials

Acknowledgements

➤ Dr Oana Istrate

➤ PPRC

➤ QUILL

➤ THE ROYAL SOCIETY

➤ Department for the Economy

Thank you

loconnor15@qub.ac.uk

